

DEVELOPMENT OF DIVERGENT THINKING IN STUDENTS THROUGH THE COMPLEX SOLUTION OF PHYSICAL PROBLEMS

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Abstract: In the article, the electrostatic field strength of a uniformly charged disk is calculated by using analytical and numerical modeling methods at different distances. Using approximate calculation formulas, we estimate the transition limits of no more than 5 – 6 % relative error in switching from one formula to another for electric field strength depending on the distance from the disk. In addition, with the help of graphs obtained analytically and numerically, it is shown that there is no significant deviation of the values at the transition limit. Such an approach to problem-solving and analysis helps students to further develop divergent thinking.

Keywords: PISA, convergent and divergent thinking, cognitive literacy, electric field strength, point charge, charge density, relative error.

Introduction

Currently, the concept of education in secondary schools in the educational system of foreign countries is radically changing. These changes can also be seen in differences in international studies of TIMSS, PIRLS, and PISA, which evaluate the effectiveness of education in countries. While the effectiveness of education at the beginning of the XXI century was studied on the basis of TIMSS and PIRLS, it is now studied mainly on the basis of the international studies of PISA. The main difference between these Assessment Systems is the assessment of what activity the reader has, and in the TIMSS and PIRLS systems, mainly the knowledge gained by readers is checked on the basis of standard issues, while in the PISA system, students' gained knowledge on the skills of applying knowledge to the natural-social processes around us are assessed [1]. Researchers believe that in the previous assessment system, the main emphasis was on the level of development of convergent thinking of students, since students with developed such thinking will have the skill to work in stages using certain algorithms on their own, based on the knowledge that has mastered the standard issue. In the collection of issues used in educational literature, physics, mathematics and chemistry, 85-90% of issues are mainly focused on the development of convergent thinking [2,3].

Issues corresponding to the current requirements of modern education, that is, issues aimed at the development of divergent thinking, account for 10-

15% of general issues, but this indicator is significantly less than the educational literature in foreign countries.

In our Republic, a lot of attention has been paid to school education in recent years, and in order to determine how well the effectiveness of our educational system is consistent with international requirements, schoolchildren began to participate in PISA international studies to test their cognitive literacy and skills. According to the results of PISA studies, it was found that the indicator of our Republic is not at a satisfactory level. The low result, according to the analysis, is largely due to objective reasons, and the use of the data is that the collection of educational literature and issues was created mainly on the basis of a system that remained from the days of the former Union [4]. Because Russia, where the education system developed, also recorded low results in PISA studies, like the CIS countries, entering the top 10 in the TIMSS and PIRLS studies. However, while students from Singapore, Taiwan, Japan, and South Korea were ranked in the top 10 in all types of International Studies, Finnish students began to achieve high results mainly in PISA studies [5]. It is assumed that in the educational systems of the countries named above, such as Japan, and Singapore, students are given great importance to the level of assimilation of new knowledge in the lower and middle classes, and then skills of application are formed. Therefore, in order to enhance the effectiveness of the educational system, it is necessary to create a set of textbooks, manuals and set of problems that will proportionally develop the level of thinking of both types in a proportional way or to use different types of physical issues in practical classes.

Research method

As we know, there will be a limit to the application of the formula used in theoretical scientific research. For example, for the air resistance at small speeds $F = \alpha v$, at larger speeds $F = \alpha v^2$ or at ultra-large speeds $F = \alpha v^n$ ($n > 2$) expressions are used. Given that in some problems, it is required to evaluate the application range of each formula. When working on such problems involving evaluation, the learner will have to rely mainly on his mathematical knowledge. As an example of such types of problems, let's see the following question regarding determining the electric field strength of a charged body. It would be advisable to use the problems presented in the sample mainly in further development of divergent thinking in groups where physics is taught as a major.

Problem: While determining the electric field strength of a charged disk, determine at what distance it can be considered as a charged infinite plane, a charged body and a point charge.

Solution: As can be seen from the condition of the problem, no physical quantities were given for the charged disc. However, it is necessary for the student to independently determine what parameters should be used.

Looking at this issue as a physical assignment, that is, a small study, we put 3 concrete issues to solve it and compare the results obtained for these issues. The most basic problem in comparison is to increase the degree of accuracy of the use of the formula or reduce the error. The accuracy of using the formula depends on the distance and the dimensions of the charged body, and the fact that at some point at some distance from the body, an electric field is charged is considered for two cases, but the dimensions of the body are taken as invariant. The relative error for E_1 and E_3 quantities related to E_2 , detected for the point being looked at is estimated to be around 2 - 8% percent.

Result and its discussion

So, the questions will be in the following context:

1. The thin disc is charged with a surface charge density of σ . Determine an electric field strength at a very short distance from the surface of the disc.
2. A thin disk with a radius of R is charged with the surface charge density σ . On the axis passing through the centre of the disc, find the electric field strength at the point lying at a distance d from the center of the disc.
3. Find the electric field strength at a distance sufficiently far ($d \gg R$) from the disc of radius R charged with the surface charge density σ .

For Question 1, We consider the disc as a charged infinite plane and find the electric field strength using the expression of $E_1 = \frac{\sigma}{2\epsilon_0}$

For Question 2, we use the traditional integration method in finding the electric field strength (Fig.1).

Fig. 1

Namely, $dE = k \frac{dq}{x^2} = \frac{\sigma 2\pi r dr}{r^2 + d^2}$, where $dE_x = dE \cos \alpha$ and $dE_y = dE \sin \alpha$.

Since the symmetry with respect to the point being viewed is fulfilled, it yields $dE_y = \int dE_y = 0$. Hence, $E = E_x = \int dE \cos \alpha$. We find the expression $\cos \alpha = \frac{d}{\sqrt{r^2 + d^2}}$ from the figure and will have the formula below:

$$E_2 = \frac{\sigma}{2\epsilon_0} \left(1 - \frac{d}{\sqrt{R^2 + d^2}} \right);$$

For Question 3, the field strength of a charged point can be used. Namely, the expression, $E_3 = k \frac{q}{d^2} = \frac{1}{4\pi\epsilon_0} \frac{\sigma\pi R_0^2}{d^2} = \frac{\sigma R_0^2}{4\epsilon_0 d^2}$ can be used.

The main purpose of a given assignment is to define the limit of application of the expressions E_1 and E_3 , and to derive expressions for E_1 and E_3 by using the expression of E_2 . With this in mind, we take the error allowed when moving from E_2 to E_1 or from E_2 to E_3 to be around 3 ÷ 8 % and evaluate the $\frac{R}{d}$ - ratio.

We estimate the value of n by assuming that it is around 5-10%.

So, we take this as the form of $\frac{|E_1 - E_2|}{E_2} \approx 0.05$

(1)

We also use approximate calculation methods, namely for $x \ll 1$ we can use the following relationship [6].

$$(1 + x)^\alpha = 1 + \alpha x \quad (2)$$

$$E_2 = \frac{\sigma}{2\epsilon_0} \left(1 - \frac{d}{\sqrt{R^2 + d^2}} \right) = \frac{\sigma}{2\epsilon_0} \left(1 - \frac{d}{R \sqrt{1 + \left(\frac{d}{R}\right)^2}} \right) \quad (3)$$

If we take $\frac{d}{R} \ll 1$ into account, we will have the following expression.

$$E_2 = \frac{\sigma}{2\epsilon_0} \left(1 - \frac{d}{R} \left(1 - \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{d}{R}\right)^2 \right) \right) \quad (4)$$

Then, $\frac{E_1 - E_2}{E_1} = \frac{d}{R} - \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{d}{R} \right)^3$ (5) equation comes out.

From the equations (1) and (5) we can have $\frac{d}{R} - \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{d}{R} \right)^3 = \frac{1}{20}$ and $\frac{d}{R} = x$ is taken and we get

$$x - \frac{1}{2} x^3 - \frac{5}{100} = 0 \quad (6)$$

The expression $x^3 \ll x$ yields from the relationship $\frac{d}{R} \ll 1$.

Hence $x \approx \frac{5}{100}$ or $\frac{d}{R} \approx \frac{1}{20} \Rightarrow R \approx 20d$ is taken.

Therefore, $E_1 = \frac{\sigma}{2\epsilon_0}$ formula can be applied up to the maximum distance of $d = \frac{R}{20}$ from the finite plane.

We can also find the minimum limit of the same charged disc at which it can be considered as a point charge while calculating the field strength. In this approximation, the $d \gg R$ relation is fulfilled. In that case, we substitute the resulting expression for E_2 as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} E_2 &= \frac{\sigma}{2\epsilon_0} \left(1 - \frac{d}{\sqrt{R^2 + d^2}} \right) = \frac{\sigma}{2\epsilon_0} \left(1 - \frac{d}{d\sqrt{1 + \left(\frac{R}{d}\right)^2}} \right) = \frac{\sigma}{2\epsilon_0} \left(1 - \frac{1}{\sqrt{1 + \left(\frac{R}{d}\right)^2}} \right) = \\ &= \frac{\sigma}{2\epsilon_0} \left(1 - \left(1 + \left(\frac{R}{d}\right)^2 \right)^{-\frac{1}{2}} \right) = \frac{\sigma}{2\epsilon_0} \left(1 - \left(1 - \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{R}{d}\right)^2 \right) \right) = \frac{1}{4\pi\epsilon_0} \frac{\sigma\pi R_0^2}{d^2}; \end{aligned}$$

and we will have the following expression:

$$E_2 = \frac{\sigma}{4\epsilon_0} \left(\frac{R}{d} \right)^2 \quad (7)$$

The formula obtained by the help of E_2 is the same as the formula obtained for the E_3 before. Taking this into account, we use the evaluation method for the relation $\left(\frac{R}{d} \right)^2 \ll 1$ when calculating the minimal distance. To increase the degree of accuracy of the evaluation, the ratio $\left(\frac{R}{d} \right)^2$ is rounded until one hundredth, that is $\left(\frac{R}{d} \right)^2 \approx 0.01$. Thus, $\frac{R}{d} \approx 0.1$ or $d \approx 10R$ will come out. If the degree of accuracy is small, the permissible error will be greater.

For convenience in computation, we choose the relation of $\left(\frac{R}{d} \right)^2 \approx 0.04$ and we will have the relation, $d \approx 5R$.

The difference between E_1 and E_2 , E_2 and E_3 is evident when a graph of the field strength versus distance from the charged disk can also be plotted by a digital modelling using all formulae.

Conditionally, taking the expression as $\frac{\sigma}{2\epsilon_0} = 1$ makes it easier to choose a scale.

Conclusion

It is obvious from the solution of the problem, only simple standard formulae were used in the assessment, but when evaluating a relative error, approximate estimation calculation formulas should be used more efficiently. In addition, by working on these types of issues, along with the development of generalized research skills in students, the skills highlighted above are further improved in processes such as working on error levels, comparing variative answers and proving the reliability of the answer. Also, in the minds of students, the fact that together with the physical model, the mathematical model is also fundamentally essential is formed, and therefore they will have a clear and solid picture of the concept that it is necessary to pay great attention to the use of the mathematical apparatus in theoretical researches.

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